

BEHAVIOUR OF FRP-REINFORCED CONCRETE ARCHES

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ABSTRACT

Deterioration of underground tunnel linings made of steel-reinforced concrete arch segments due to the corrosion of steel reinforcement has become a critical issue. To address this issue, concrete arch segments reinforced with durable fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) bars have attracted increasing research attention. When FRP bars are used, the strict limit on chloride ions in concrete production can be relaxed, so that seawater and sea-sand may be used as raw materials in the construction, which offers compelling economic and environmental advantages. This paper presents a combined theoretical and experimental study on the structural behaviour of FRP-reinforced seawater sea-sand concrete (SSC) arches. The experimental work involved a test on an FRP-SSC arch specimen, which provides the first insight into the behaviour and failure mode of such arches.

KEYWORDS

seawater sea-sand concrete; arches; FRP-reinforced concrete structures

INTRODUCTION

The corrosion of steel reinforcement has become a critical issue for underground tunnel linings made of steel-reinforced concrete arch segments. Because of their excellent corrosion resistance, the use of fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) bars in arches has been recently explored by a number of studies (Caratelli et al., 2016; Caratelli et al., 2017; Meda et al., 2019; Tengilimoğlu, 2019). Notably, the use of FRP bars not only addresses the steel corrosion problem, but also opens a new avenue for the concrete production using seawater and sea-sand as the raw materials, which are locally available in coastal regions (Teng et al., 2011). The innovative use of FRP and seawater sea-sand concrete (SSC) offers compelling economic and environmental advantages for the construction of coastal and marine infrastructure (Teng et al., 2011). Against this background, this paper presents a recent study on the structural behaviour of FRP-reinforced SSC arches. The study includes the testing of an arch specimen in which glass FRP (GFRP) reinforcement and SSC were used, as well as theoretical analysis on the load capacity of such arches.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Specimen Details

The test specimen (Figures 1 and 2) had a span length of 3000 mm, a sectional width of 300 mm, a sectional depth of 100 mm and a rise-span ratio of 0.25, representing a scaled model of typical underground half-lining structures with a scale factor of 1:10. Two pairs of GFRP rebars with a diameter of 6 mm were used as the longitudinal reinforcement close to the top and bottom of the cross-section, respectively, while closed GFRP stirrups with a diameter of 8 mm and spaced at 200 mm intervals along the arch axis were used as the transverse reinforcement and for locating the longitudinal bars (Figure 2). The longitudinal GFRP rebars were curved bars manufactured and delivered in a pre-bent state. In preparing the specimen, the GFRP reinforcement cage was first fabricated and then placed into a steel mould for concrete casting; the cast specimen was then cured following ASTM 192 (ASTM C192/C192M-12, 2012).

Figure 1 Sketch of test specimen

Figure 2 Details of test specimen (Unit: mm)

Material Properties

The bent GFRP bars were composed of continuous unidirectional glass-fibre strands bonded together using a thermosetting vinyl ester resin, employing a pultrusion process. The mechanical properties of the GFRP bars were determined according to ACI 440.3R-12 (ACI 440.3R-12, 2012). To avoid the challenges associated with measuring the properties of curved GFRP bars, straight bars produced in the same batch using the same raw materials as the curved bars were tested to determine their tensile strength and modulus of elasticity (Table 1), following Spagnuolo et al. (2018).

Table 1: Material Properties

Material	Strength		Elastic Modulus		Strain at peak stress	
	Mean (MPa)	COV	Mean (GPa)	COV	Mean	COV
FRP bar	1011.4	0.017	49.83	0.012	2.03%	0.012
Concrete	45.2	0.015	29.80	0.043	0.24%	0.088

Seawater sea-sand concrete was used for the specimen, and the mix proportions are given in Table 2. The concrete mixture comprised commercial crushed granite with a maximum size of 10 mm as the coarse aggregate and sea-sand as the fine aggregate. Type I 52.5 CEM and pulverized fly ash (PFA) were used, while the seawater was obtained locally in Hong Kong; superplasticizer ADVA 109 was used as a water reducer. The compressive properties of concrete were determined through compression tests of three standard cylinders (150 mm × 300 mm), and the results are given in Table 1.

Table 2: Mix Proportion (in kg/m³)

W/C	W/B	Coarse Aggregates	Fine Aggregates	Cement	PFA	Water	Water Reducer
0.665	0.482	1070	717	290	110	193	0.565

Test Setup

A quasi-static test was conducted on the arch specimen using a compression test system with a load capacity of 500 kN (Figure 3); the arch was considered a fixed arch. During the test, the arch specimen was subjected to a monotonically increasing load applied at the mid-span. The load was applied with a

displacement control rate of 0.4 mm/min in the initial stage which was then gradually increased to 2 mm/min during the test.

Figure 3 Test setup

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the initial stage, the load increased linearly with the displacement until a load of 11.05 kN (mid-span displacement: 3.26 mm) (Point 1 in Figure 4), at which a through-width flexural crack was noticed near the mid-span region; the crack propagated afterwards from the bottom to the top, ultimately extending to the concrete cover of the top reinforcement within the section (Figure 5). Further examination of the cracked section revealed that there was a GFRP stirrup at the section. The second and third major cracks with a substantial width occurred at the arch shoulders on both sides of the mid-span, of which the second one occurred almost at the same time as the first crack, while the third one occurred a bit later. Subsequently, four more major cracks occurred during the loading process, and Figure 6 shows the locations of cracks and their sequence of occurrence. Notably, the occurrence of each major crack was accompanied with a significant load drop (see Figure 4); this observation is different from that in normal steel-reinforced concrete arches and may be attributed to two main factors: (1) the specimen was designed to be an under-reinforced concrete arch with a relatively small reinforcement ratio; (2) the elastic modulus of GFRP bars (i.e., approximately 50 GPa) was considerably lower than that of steel bars (i.e., approximately 200 GPa). Consequently, the GFRP bars were unable to immediately take the load released by the tensile concrete when a major crack occurred. Nevertheless, with the increasing local deformation at the cracked section, the strains in the GFRP bars gradually increased, and the load capacity of the arch could be recovered after the first six cracks (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Load-deflection curve

Figure 5 Fracture of concrete near the mid-span at the failure point

(a) Location of cracks of the left-half specimen

(b) Location of cracks of the right-half specimen

Figure 6 Specimen after test

It is also worth noting that all the cross-sections with a major crack had a GFRP stirrup located there. It is believed that the presence of these GFRP stirrups, with fibres in the hoop direction and thus having a relatively small stiffness/strength in the longitudinal direction of the arch, somewhat weakened the cross-sections in terms of their bending capacity, so that cracks tended to occur at these weak sections. This effect might not always be considerable, but appeared to be pronounced in the test specimen due to its relatively small cross-section.

Despite the several major cracks and the associated load drops, the arch could sustain a substantial load until a displacement of 72.25 mm (i.e., Failure point in Figure 4), at which the rupture of two bottom GFRP longitudinal bars near the mid-span occurred when the cross-section reached its bending capacity.

ANALYSIS OF LOAD CAPACITY

The relationship between the applied load and the internal forces/bending moments of the arch can be obtained using the force method for indeterminate structures by applying deformation compatibility and force equilibrium equations (Tang et al., 2021). Due to the symmetry of the structure and the load, only half of the arch was considered in the analysis, as shown in Figure 7. The horizontal and vertical reaction forces R_x and R_y as well as the bending moment M_R at the support can be first calculated using the force method to be: $R_x = 0.915P$, $R_y = 0.5P$, $M_R = -0.0651rP$, where $r = 1875mm$ is the radius of the arch. With these, the internal axial force N and bending moment M at any section of the arch can be calculated by:

$$\begin{cases} N = R_x \cos(\varphi) + R_y \sin(\varphi) \\ M = R_x y - R_y x + M_R \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where x and y are the coordinates of the section and φ is the central angle at a given point (Figure 7). Using Eq. 1, it can be derived that the maximum sagging bending moment is located at the mid-span, while the largest hogging bending moment is located at the arch shoulder with $\varphi = 29.31^\circ$. During the test, the first major crack occurred near the mid-span, while the second and third major flexural cracks occurred approximately symmetrically with respect to the mid-span with an angle of $\varphi = 28.69^\circ$,

demonstrating the reliability of the analysis. The slight differences between the analytical and test results in the locations are believed to be due to the existence of GFRP stirrups which weakened some of the cross-sections, as discussed in the preceding section.

Figure 7 Diagram of analysis

Using Eq. 1, the internal axial force and bending moment at the mid-span section at the applied load 14.76 kN of the failure point (i.e. Point 7 in Figure 5) can be calculated to be: $N_{Applied} = 13.62 \text{ kN (compression)}$, $M_{Applied} = 2.28 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$. If the self-weight of the arch is considered, the actual maximum internal forces/moment are slightly different as: $N_{max} = 14.72 \text{ kN (compression)}$, $M_{max} = 2.29 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$.

The section capacity of the arch can be calculated using the section analysis method with the following assumptions: (1) the stress distribution of concrete within the compression zone is assumed to follow a rectangular stress block, as specified in the Australian standard (AS 3600-09, 2009); (2) the tensile strength of concrete is ignored; (3) the bond between GFRP bars and concrete is perfect; (4) the GFRP bars exhibit elastic behaviour with the same elastic modulus in both tension and compression.

In the test, the final failure of the arch occurred when the bottom GFRP bars ruptured. On the other hand, it was observed that the concrete cover was crushed and detached from the arch during the test (Figure 4). Therefore, it is not unreasonable to assume that the maximum strain of the remaining concrete reached its ultimate strain [i.e., 0.3% according to ACI 440.11R-22 (ACI 440.11R-22, 2022)] at the final failure. With the above assumption and considering the contribution of the remaining concrete and the GFRP bars, the section capacity of the arch at the final failure can be calculated to be: $N_u = 15.35 \text{ kN (compression)}$, $M_u = 2.57 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$. It is evident that the calculated ultimate axial force and bending moment of the mid-section are both close to, while slightly lower than the test results. The slight differences between the calculated and test results are understandable as the analysis was based on the geometrical properties of the undeformed arch with the effects geometrical nonlinearity being neglected. It should also be noted that, although the above analysis is useful for gaining a basic understanding of the test results, it is semi-empirical in nature as it takes some assumptions based on the test observation.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper presents a combined experimental and analytical study on the behaviour of an FRP-reinforced seawater sea-sand concrete (SSC) arch. The experiment confirms that FRP-reinforced concrete arches, characterized by their excellent corrosion resistance, are structurally sound and offer a promising alternative to traditional arch structures. It is, however, found that significant load drops may occur when a major crack appears in under-reinforced GFRP-reinforced concrete arches with a relatively small reinforcement ratio, suggesting that it is desirable to design such arches to be over-reinforced. It is also noted that the incorporation of FRP stirrups may somewhat weaken the section in

terms of the flexural capacity, especially for under-reinforced thin-walled arches; innovative forms of transverse reinforcement may be developed to address this issue in the future. Furthermore, the presented analysis method can be used to understand the behaviour of the arch and to estimate its load capacity, but it is semi-empirical in nature. To fully understand and simulate the behaviour of FRP-reinforced SSC arches, a more comprehensive study is ongoing by the authors' group, involving a systematic experimental program with a focus on the over-reinforced arches and theoretical modelling using an enhanced formulation of the deflection method, where the second order effect is taken into account.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful for the financial support received from the Hong Kong Research Grants Council (Project No.: T22-502/18-R). The authors also acknowledge the opportunity provided by the PolyU-ZJU Joint PhD Program for the first author to undertake a joint PhD program under the supervision of the two corresponding authors.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.